

Neutron irradiated perovskite films and solar cells on PET substrates

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Abstract

Flexible perovskite solar cells feature high power-per-weight ratio and low cost manufacturing, which make them very attractive for space and avionic applications. It is thus paramount to assess their response to the harsh space environment. Although an increasing number of studies have been investigating the effect of electron and proton radiation on perovskite solar cells, very few have dealt with neutron irradiation and even less with flexible devices. In this paper, the stability of unencapsulated flexible perovskite solar cells against fast neutron irradiation at two different fluence levels is evaluated, comparing commercially available spiro-OMeTAD and an in-house modified P3HT as the hole transport materials. We observed degradation for both materials and at both fluences. Modified-P3HT cells experienced remarkable smaller voltage and current losses compared to spiro-OMeTAD; still, their overall performance degraded similarly to spiro-OMeTAD devices at higher fluence,

whilst it suffered a much higher drop than spiro-OMeTAD at lower fluence, as a consequence of a larger decrease in fill factor, ascribable to a sub-optimal perovskite/polymer interface. Spectral response and behavior at different light intensities of modified-P3HT cells suggest the polymer to be potentially more resilient than spiro-OMeTAD under fast neutron irradiation, once the perovskite/polymer is improved, although further investigations are needed to gain more insights and push the development and adoption of flexible PSCs for space and avionic applications.

Keywords

Flexible perovskite solar cells; neutron irradiation; space; hole transport material; small molecule; P3HT.

1. Introduction

High efficiency, low cost and solution processability are key advantages of perovskite-based devices over conventional silicon-based photovoltaics, and have attracted soaring attention from both academia and industry[1–4]. While long-term stability of these devices is still an open issue, the increasing understanding of materials and degradation mechanisms is leading to promising improvements in both accelerated indoor and outdoor tests[5–9].

When moving from rigid glass to flexible plastic substrates, record power conversion efficiency (PCE) drops from over 25%[10] to 20.7%[11]; nonetheless, flexible perovskite solar cells (f-PSC)[12–14] allow for low temperature and low cost manufacturing processes[15–17], open up to a wider range of applications[18,19] and are more sustainable[20]. Moreover, thanks to substrate conformability and superior power-to-weight ratio[21], f-PSCs show enormous potential for avionic and space applications, where the payload is a major concern[22]. Interestingly, some of the extrinsic factors affecting PSC long-term stability, such as humidity and oxygen, which can potentially undermine their applicability on earth[7], do not apply in space[22]. On the other hand, space is a harsh environment[23], featuring large radiation doses of highly energetic particles, such as electrons, protons, and heavy ions, i.e. cosmic rays, and extreme temperature cycles, whose effect on PSC performance and stability need to be assessed.

A rising number of studies, carried out to investigate the effect of outer space radiations on PSCs, has reported good tolerance to both electrons and protons. Glass-encapsulated cells with glass/FTO/TiO₂/perovskite/P3HT/Au structure survived fluence levels of up to 10¹⁶ and 10¹⁵ particles·cm⁻² of electrons (1 MeV) and protons (50 keV) respectively, levels known to completely destroy c-Si, GaAs and InGaP/GaAs in spacecrafts[23]. Cells on quartz substrates, with AZO/SnO₂/CsMAFAPbIBr/spiro-OMeTAD/Au structure, did not show significant loss in efficiency when exposed to up to 10¹³ particles·cm⁻² of protons (150 keV)[22]. Devices on glass, with ITO/PEDOT:PSS/MAPI/PCBM/BCP/Ag layer sequence, withstood fluences of up to 10¹³ particles·cm⁻² of high-energy (68 MeV) protons [24,25], outperforming c-Si devices; the same cell structure on PET (the only report on flexible substrates so far) also demonstrated to be stable against fluences of up to 10¹² particles·cm⁻² of low-energy (100 keV) protons, expected to be stopped in the shallower regions of the devices, and thus to lead to degradation more likely than high-energy protons[26]. Such remarkable resilience to both electrons and protons has been ascribed to the self-healing properties of the mixed covalent-ionic lattice of the perovskite materials, which allows self-passivation of the radiation-induced defects[24].

Less attention has been dedicated to assessing the interaction between neutrons and PSCs, even though fast neutrons (i.e. with energies > 10 MeV) represent one of the most severe forms of radiation at aircraft altitudes, in avionic and space environments. For example, the annual fluence received by the equipment on the International Space Station (ISS) is estimated to be $\sim 2.8 \times 10^{11}$ neutrons·cm⁻² with energies from 0.1 eV to 10⁵ MeV[27]. As a reference, at ground level the fluence is 3.85×10^5 neutrons·cm⁻²[27]. Fast neutrons are known to be a threat for microelectronic components in both space and terrestrial environment, as they can induce transient faults, such as bit-flips, or permanent degradation, such as displacement damage (one or more atoms are removed from their original locations by the impinging particle) caused by the accumulation of charge, i.e. total ionizing dose[26,28].

A recent preliminary work evaluated the resilience of planar PSCs, with inverted p-i-n structure on glass substrates, to thermal and fast neutrons, using the VESUVIO beamline at the ISIS Spallation Neutron Source[29]. Glass-encapsulated devices, with cell structure ITO/

PEDOT:PSS/ CH₃NH₃PbI_{3-x}Cl_x/ PCBM/ aluminium, showed good stability to 435 minutes of neutron irradiation, i.e. 1.5×10^9 neutrons·cm⁻², corresponding to approximately 80 years of fast neutron exposure on the ISS. Fast neutrons led to irreversible effects, possibly due to atomic displacement in the active materials, albeit mitigated by the formation of neutron-induced shallow traps, acting as dopants[29].

In this paper, we report on unencapsulated flexible PSCs, potentially better fit to avionic and space applications than glass-based ones, upon fast neutron irradiation at fluence levels of 1.39×10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² (same order of magnitude as in ref[29], i.e. almost 80 years of fast neutron exposure on the ISS) and 1.62×10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² (equivalent to 864 years of fast neutron exposure on the ISS), respectively. Both spiro-OMeTAD, and a benzothiadiazole-modified P3HT (BTD-P3HT)[30] were used as the hole transport material (HTM). Spiro-OMeTAD is possibly the most widely used HTM for PSC in research laboratories: although stability issues have been reported, related to additives used to dope it and increase its conductivity[31,32], record PSC devices usually employ spiro-OMeTAD as the HTM[33,34]. P3HT and its derivate polymers, on the other hand, have been reported to be an effective alternative to costly spiro-OMeTAD, thanks to high hole mobility ($0.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), relatively easy synthesis, thus lower production costs, and good thermal and light stability [35–38], and have been successfully used for planar n-i-p PSC on flexible substrates, achieving a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 11.84%[39]. Specifically, in this work, we used an in-house BTD-modified P3HT, since it showed interesting features in our previous study[30]: PCE comparable to conventional P3HT, feasibility for large area deposition, translating into 6.9% PCE on 6×6 cm² modules, and improved stability under illumination, compared to both unmodified P3HT and spiro-OMeTAD. The stability of unencapsulated f-PSC upon fast neutron irradiation was investigated via electrical characterization, spectral response and behavior at different light intensities, comparing spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT as the hole transport materials.

2. Results and discussion

Planar perovskite solar cells with n-i-p structure, i.e. SnO₂/ perovskite/ hole transport layer/ Au, were fabricated on flexible ITO-PET via spin-coating of tin oxide (SnO₂), mixed-cation

mixed-halide perovskite $\text{Cs}_{0.06}\text{FA}_{0.78}\text{MA}_{0.16}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.84}\text{Br}_{0.16})_3$ and either commercially available spiro-OMeTAD or in-house synthesised BTD-P3HT[30], topped with a thermally evaporated gold electrode. Both spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT were doped with the same additives, i.e. tert-butyl pyridine, Li-TFSI and Co(III)-TFSI, but at different concentrations, according to our previous work[37].

Figure 1 shows the PV parameters, extracted by the current density-voltage (J-V) curves, of the flexible solar cells, tested after fabrication. Spiro-OMeTAD cells display higher PCE than BTD-P3HT: 12% vs 9.2% in average for the reverse scan, 10.9% vs 8.5% in average for the forward scan, 14.3% vs 10.8% for the best device, in line with previously reported results[30]. Open circuit voltages (V_{oc}) range between 1009 and 1038 mV for spiro-OMeTAD and between 944 and 1009 mV for BTD-P3HT (Figure S1). The lower values for the polymer are possibly due to additional non-radiative recombination at the interface with perovskite: strong electronic coupling and poor physical contact between highly regioregular, flat BTD-P3HT and perovskite can slow the hole transport[40], whereas spiro-OMeTAD small molecules arrange more effectively on the perovskite, leading to a higher quality interface and promoting hole transport. BTD-P3HT deliver lower short circuit current density (J_{sc}) - ranging between 17.5 and 19.3 mA/cm^2 for spiro-OMeTAD and between 15.6 and 17.6 mA/cm^2 for BTD-P3HT - and lower fill factors (FF) - i.e. 67% and 58% in average for spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT respectively (Figure S1); this can be related to the short chain of the polymer[41], whose molecular weight is 44.9 kDa[30]. Also, the less favourable band alignment for BTD-P3HT, whose highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) lies at -5.14 eV[30] whilst it is -5.23 eV for spiro-OMeTAD, can lead to transport barriers and internal voltage drop, particularly around the maximum power point, contributing to the low FF[42]. This gap could be filled by synthesizing higher MW polymers and by engineering both HTM and PSK energy level; yet, this optimization falls outside the scope of the present paper and it will be presented elsewhere.

Figure 1. Flexible cells used in this study. (a) Scheme of the cell architecture; (b) Picture of a typical flexible device, including 4 squared cells on the same substrate, electrically isolated by laser scribing; (c) power conversion efficiency of freshly fabricated flexible cells, endowed with either commercially available spiro-OMeTAD or in-house synthesised BTD-P3HT ($R = \text{hexyl group}$).

After characterisation, cells destined to be exposed to the accelerated neutron beam were carefully packaged, without exposing them to light, and shipped over to the ChipIR facility at the ISIS Spallation Neutron Source of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory in Didcot (United Kingdom).

ChipIR beamline provides a high energy neutron spectrum of energy that resembles the atmospheric one, although accelerated (Figure S2), and is mainly used for the analysis of single event effects (SEEs) in electronic component at ground and flight level [43]. The neutron flux available at ChipIR is about $9 \times 10^9 \text{ neutrons} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, almost 9 orders of magnitude higher than the atmospheric neutron flux at sea level, i.e. $13 \text{ neutrons} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, allowing to gather a statistically significant amount of neutrons interactions in a very short time. ChipIR neutrons interactions resemble also the radiation environment of other planets, such as Mars, and of the interior of space crafts, such as the International Space Station, where neutron spectra are similar to the terrestrial one (Figure S2). This is because in all these environments the production of neutrons is based on the spallation reaction of high energy primary protons. This would not be the case, for example, for a fission reactor, where the neutron energy

spectrum does not extend to the high energies (say $E > 10$ MeV). Unlike other beamlines, such as VESUVIO, ChipIR provides a neutron flux nearly free from thermal neutrons (i.e. low energy neutrons produced by the interaction of high energy neutrons with materials) and allows focusing on high energy neutrons (fast neutrons), which are strongly correlated to high energy protons, reportedly affecting electronic devices [44]. Also, the high energy neutron flux of ChipIR is about 100 times higher than VESUVIO, allowing to deliver the same fluence in a much shorter time.

Unencapsulated flexible cells were thus exposed to fluences of about 10^9 neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$ and 10^{10} neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$ to highlight potential incremental effects. Samples of ITO-PET substrates, bare and coated with SnO $_2$, were also irradiated: only slight differences in the transmittance, within 2%, were observed (Figure S3), confirming the resilience of both the flexible substrate, where ITO acts as a protection layer for the PET[45], and the SnO $_2$ electron transport layer [22].

On the contrary, perovskite layers, deposited on SnO $_2$, experienced degradation after irradiation, as proved by the UV-vis absorbance (Figure S4a) and XRD spectra (Figure S5). The band gaps were extracted from the absorbance data, and were found to be between 1.62 eV for the irradiated films (1.622 eV for 10^{10} neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$, 1.626 eV for 10^9 neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$) and 1.63 eV for the control film: since the band gap depends on the Br/I ratio, this could indicate a slight compositional change[46]. The decrease in absorbance after irradiation is reduced when the perovskite film is covered by spiro-OMeTAD (Figure S4b) whilst is augmented for the perovskite/ BTd-P3HT samples (Figure S4c). The protective function of spiro-OMeTAD is confirmed by XRD spectra (Figure S5). The diffraction peak ascribable to the (003) PbI $_2$, located at $2\theta = 12.6^\circ$, overtops the characteristic peak of the (100) perovskite phase, located at $2\theta = 14.1^\circ$ for all the examined samples. Nonetheless, the ratio between the integrated areas of these two peaks, which is 2 for the perovskite layer before irradiation, jumps close to 8 for the 10^{10} neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$ irradiated perovskite film, but is much lower, i.e. ≈ 4 , for the irradiated PSK/HTM layer, accounting for sizeable shielding effect of the HTM against perovskite degradation. The XRD analysis was limited to the most performing HTM, i.e. spiro-OMeTAD, and to the worst scenario, i.e. 10^{10} neutrons \cdot cm $^{-2}$.

Concerning the complete devices, the f-PSC performance could not be measured immediately before and after irradiation, due to the lack of a solar simulator at the ISIS facility. It took 21 days before the irradiated cells could be retested, due to the shipping time and the post-irradiation quarantine required for safe handling, according to ISIS safety protocols. In the meantime, the control cells were kept in the fabrication laboratory, stored in a box with silica in the dark at ambient conditions. After this 21-days lag, we performed J-V measurements on the control f-PSCs again to assess the effect of the storage time and disregard any contributions to degradation ascribable to the mere ageing process, by comparing the J-V curves to those recorded right after fabrication. As shown in Figure 2(a), the performance of the control spiro-OMeTAD cells after the storage in the dark worsened overall, from average PCE of 12.2% and 10.9% (reverse and forward scans) to 9.8% and 9.2%, respectively, accounting for a loss between 15 and 20%, mainly due to J_{SC} and FF reduction (Figure S). The J-V curves reported in Figure 2(c), which represent an average of four devices, show a reduction of current density and FF as well as an increase of the series resistances. Also, the standard deviation associated to the average J-V curve increased from 9% for the fresh devices to 17% for the cells after the storage in dark, in line with the increased spread of the PV values shown in Figure S7. The observed degradation can be ascribed to the presence of the additives, broadly used to enhance spiro-OMeTAD conductivity, which are known to degrade when exposed to oxygen and humidity [47,48]. The same additives that induce degradation in spiro-OMeTAD have been found to improve the stability of P3HT[37], that has already been reported to be more stable, thanks to its low permeability to oxygen and strong hydrophobicity[35,49]. The polymer likely shields the dopants from getting in contact with humidity and air better than spiro-OMeTAD. Actually, control BTM-P3HT cells did not suffer from the storage time, passing from 9.6% and 9.3% average PCE (reverse and forward scans) for pristine cells, to 10.4% and 9.1% average PCE after storage, corresponding to a percentage loss within 2% in forward scan and a gain of 8.7% in reverse scan, as a result of small J_{SC} reductions within 5% and FF increment up to 11% in percentage compared to the pristine cells (Figure S6). Only the hysteresis slightly increased, as also evident from the average J-V curves in Figure 2(d): the two scan directions yield different PCE almost exclusively due to variation in FF (see Figure S7). It has been reported that, for planar cells, the hysteresis is usually more severe than for mesoporous devices, especially due to low FF at forward scans,

caused by accumulation of capacitive charges [50], which, in this case, could be the result of a worsening of the perovskite/polymer interface. Unlike the spiro-OMeTAD case, the standard deviation of the average J-V curves went from 6% for the fresh cells to 7% for the BTD-P3HT devices after the storage in dark.

Figure 2. Effect of storage time on control cells. Control cells were tested after fabrication and after being stored in a box, in the dark at ambient conditions, for as long as the time needed to ship the other cells to the ISIS facility, where they were irradiated, and then back to the fabrication laboratory. (a), (b) Power conversion efficiency for control cells endowed with spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT respectively; values for both forward scan (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse scan (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported. (c), (d) J-V curves of the same cells, representing an average of four devices.

To assess the effect of neutron irradiation, we then carried out J-V scans on the irradiated devices and compared their electrical behaviour to that of the control cells, measured after

the storage in dark, and not straight after fabrication, to disregard the contribution to degradation due to the mere ageing process during the 21-days interval described above, ageing which accounted for a 15-to-20% loss for spiro-OMeTAD devices whereas did not affect BTd-P3HT cells (Figure S6). In Figure 3, average J-V curves are reported as well as the variation in the PV parameters (Figure S8) for the irradiated samples with respect to the relative controls.

The efficiency of spiro-OMeTAD cells, irradiated at 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² fluence, decreased by 7% in average in forward scan and increased by about 5% in average in reverse scan, mainly due to the 30% increase of the relative FF, a usual consequence of a J_{SC} decrease, as in this case. PCE, that is directly dependent on J_{SC} , V_{OC} , and FF, experienced the above mentioned 5% increase as a result of the much relevant FF increase (+30%), compared to the decrease in J_{SC} and V_{OC} (-15% and -4%, respectively). At higher fluence, i.e. 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻², the PCE dropped in average by 16% (forward) and 11% (reverse). The performance of irradiated BTd-P3HT cells also decreased, with more pronounced PCE drop and hysteresis for the 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² fluence, i.e. -31% and -18% for the forward and reverse scans respectively. Overall, BTd-P3HT cells degraded more than spiro-OMeTAD devices under 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation, and similarly to spiro-OMeTAD under 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation (13-16% drop).

Still, open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) displayed a quite uniform 2.5% decrement for BTd-P3HT cells, regardless the fluence and the scan direction, whereas for spiro-OMeTAD it decreased by about 4% and 8% respectively with the increase of the irradiation fluence. Shorter charge carrier lifetime and thus higher recombination rate are very likely for all irradiated samples, but to a higher extent for spiro-OMeTAD. High energy neutrons are known to induce atomic displacement, resulting in the creation of vacancies and interstitial sites (Frenkel pairs)[29], and are also capable of ionizing the perovskite crystal lattice, damaging its crystal structure by upsetting the ionic and covalent bonds between atoms[26]. Both phenomena lead to energy states in the band gap near the valence or conduction band that act as recombination centres, lowering the V_{OC} .

Short circuit current density (J_{SC}) dropped by about 10% for all BTd-P3HT devices, with the exception of the 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated samples (-4.5%, reverse). Spiro-OMeTAD cells

experienced an even more severe loss, with larger difference between forward and reverse scan values: -8% in forward and -16% in reverse for 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻², -7% in forward and -22% in reverse for 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻². The lower J_{SC} values point to a higher degree of degradation of the perovskite film for the spiro-OMeTAD cells than for the BTd-P3HT; the higher hysteresis can be ascribed to excess irradiation-induced vacancy and interstitial defects, causing ion and charge carrier migration in the active layer and altering the build-in potential[22,51,52].

For spiro-OMeTAD devices under both fluences, such J_{SC} values, lower than the controls, especially in reverse, caused positive variations for the fill factor (FF). Irradiated cells in reverse scans showed in average 75% FF for 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² fluence and 73% FF for 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² fluence, that correspond respectively to +31% and +28% compared to control, i.e. 57.3% FF; in forward scans, instead, FF values of irradiated cells (54% and 51% respectively) were comparable to the control, i.e. 51.5% FF. For all BTd-P3HT devices, FF variations were instead negative, although below 6%, with the only exception of the 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated cells in reverse scan, which lost around 22% compared to the control and displayed a higher hysteresis degree than the 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated ones.

The trends of series and shunt resistances (R_S and R_{Sh} respectively) are reported in Figure S. With the exception of one outlier for the control cells, the R_S of irradiated spiro-OMeTAD samples slightly decreases for both fluences, passing from 10-20 Ω range to being between 10-15 Ω . For the BTd-P3HT cells, instead, the R_S of irradiated cells slightly increases, remaining anyway below 20 Ω . This can be also observed in the J-V curves in Figure 3c and d: the curve slope around V_{OC} is less steep for increased R_S and thus hindered current collection by the electrodes. On the other hand, the trend of R_{Sh} for the spiro-OMeTAD control cells shows a large difference between the values in forward and reverse scans, i.e. much higher R_{Sh} values for the reverse scan, which does not change after 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation whereas the gap narrows after 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation. With the exception of one outlier for the control cells, the R_{Sh} of BTd-P3HT control cells is characterized by lower hysteresis, which increases after 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation and is reduced after 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiation.

The observed PCE reduction for both HTMs, due mainly to the J_{SC} drop, can be the result of degradation of the hole transport layer and/or of its interface with the perovskite layer, leading to shallow trap states, and has been already reported for devices under neutron[29] and proton irradiation[22].

Figure 3. **Effect of neutron irradiation on flexible cells.** (a), (b) Variation of the average values of PV parameters for the irradiated flexible cells, with either spiro-OMeTAD or BTD-P3HT as the HTL compared to control cells. (c), (d) J-V curves, representing an average of four devices, for the same flexible devices: control cells and cells irradiated at different fluences, i.e. 10^9 and 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻²·s⁻¹.

It is worth noting that neglecting the effect of the storage in the dark over the 21-days lag, needed for the irradiated samples to be shipped back and forth to ISIS, i.e. comparing the PV parameters of the irradiated cells to those of the cells freshly made, would lead to different outcomes for the investigated HTMs (Figure S10). The variation of average PV values for

irradiated BTd-P3HT cells is very similar regardless the terms of comparison, either the control cells freshly fabricated or the control cells after the storage in the dark. For irradiated spiro-OMeTAD cells, instead, the variation calculated towards the freshly made devices is much higher (15-20% drop in PCE for 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² and close to 30% PCE drop for 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻², Figure S10) than when the term of comparison is the control cells after the storage in the dark (Figure 3a). In such comparison, in which we focus on the overall degradation (most likely the result of at least the neutron irradiation and the ageing in air at ambient conditions of the flexible unencapsulated PSCs), BTd-P3HT showed smaller decrease than spiro-OMeTAD not only in both J_{SC} (<14% vs <28% drop) and V_{OC} (<2% vs <10% drop) but also in PCE: with the exception of the 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated samples, in forward scan, which reported a >30% drop, mainly due to a large FF reduction, BTd-P3HT cells experienced an overall PCE drop within 15%, whilst spiro-OMeTAD suffered a more pronounced PCE reduction, between 16% and 29%.

External quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra confirm the performance trends: initial EQE is higher for spiro-OMeTAD control cells than for BTd-P3HT, as shown in Figure 4, leading to integrated photocurrent of 17.9 and 13.8 mA·cm⁻², respectively, in line with average J_{SC} values from J-V measurements. For irradiated samples, regardless the fluence, the spectra are almost identical, lower in intensity than the controls. Nevertheless, the drop in EQE, and thus in the integrated photocurrent density, is larger for spiro-OMeTAD than for BTd-P3HT cells after irradiation (around 20% and 10% lower than the control, respectively). Reduction of EQE intensity, can indicate a higher degree of degradation of the HTM and/or of the HTM/perovskite interface. The spectrum shape of irradiated spiro-OMeTAD cells resembles the controls, with a slight red shift at low wavelengths; EQE spectra of irradiated BTd-P3HT devices are slightly tilted, with more accentuated drop at higher wavelengths. Lower values in the high wavelengths region can be ascribable to an increase of PbI_2 , which does not absorb beyond ~540 nm, in the perovskite layer, as also shown by the XRD spectra, with consequent detrimental effect on its ability of photo-generating current.

Figure 4. Characterisation of irradiated flexible cells. (a, d) EQE spectra of the control and irradiated cells endowed with spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT respectively; (b, e) Short Circuit Current density and (c, f) Open Circuit Voltage as functions of light intensity for representative flexible cells using spiro-OMeTAD and BTD-P3HT as the hole transport material.

Further insights on the effect of the neutron irradiation come from the exponent α and ideality factor n , extracted respectively from the double logarithmic J_{sc} and semilogarithmic V_{oc} trends with light intensity (Figure 4). When BTD-P3HT is used as the HTM, α is close to 1 for all samples, slightly lower for the irradiated cells (0.966 and 0.951 respectively) than the control, i.e. 0.981: space charge effects are negligible and charge transport is not compromised. For spiro-OMeTAD cells, instead, α is close to 1 for the control but, for the irradiated cells, it sharply increases, especially at low light intensities, denoting a possible increase of bimolecular recombination mechanisms [53]. A similar trend is observed for V_{oc} as a function of light intensity: BTD-P3HT cells display similar slope, thus similar values of the ideality factor for both control and 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated cell (i.e. 1.52 and 1.59 respectively) and even a lower value (i.e. 1.17) for 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated cells, pointing to similar, even reduced, recombination rates for the irradiated samples to the control. On the other hand, the increasingly steeper slope with fluence for irradiated spiro-OMeTAD cells, compared to the control, denotes an increased trap-mediated recombination, confirming the

detrimental effect of neutron-induced defects on V_{OC} and performance in general, as discussed above.

Conclusions

The performance of unencapsulated PSC devices on flexible substrates was assessed before and after neutron irradiation at two different fluences. Commercially available spiro-OMeTAD and in-house synthesized BTD-P3HT were compared. All the irradiated cells experienced degradation: the average PCE drop for both HTMs was below 15% at 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻² fluence and even smaller for spiro-OMeTAD at lower fluence, i.e. 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻². Unexpectedly, the PCE of BTD-P3HT devices at 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² fluence suffered a much higher PCE drop, resulting from a larger decrease in FF (only for 10^9 neutrons·cm⁻² irradiated samples and especially in the forward scans), very likely due to a not optimal perovskite/polymer interface, more prone to degradation. Nonetheless, BTD-P3HT cells showed smaller V_{OC} and J_{SC} losses compared to spiro-OMeTAD, as well as a smaller decrease in the spectral response, and slight changes in the behavior at different light intensities, suggesting the polymer can be potentially more resilient than spiro-OMeTAD under neutron irradiation, once the interfacial issues are addressed. It is also worth noting that BTD-P3HT devices were less affected than spiro-OMeTAD cells by the inevitable ageing over the 21-days lag (needed for the irradiated samples to be shipped back and forth to the ISIS facilities): in terms of overall degradation, the former experienced an overall PCE drop within 15%, whilst the latter suffered a more pronounced PCE reduction, between 16% and 29%. Work is ongoing to further optimize the modified polymer and also to gain more insights on the interaction between neutrons and perovskite PV, especially on flexible substrates, to speed up the adoption of such promising devices for space and avionic applications.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Experimental

Fabrication of devices

ITO PET substrates ($15 \Omega/\text{sq}$), sized $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ and laser scribed to obtain 4 electrically isolated areas on the same substrate, were cleaned by ultrasonication with isopropanol and water for 15 minutes in each solvent. The electron transport layer SnO_2 was obtained via spin coating of a SnO_2 nanoparticle aqueous dispersion (15%w, Alfa Aesar) at a speed of 6000 rpm for 35 seconds. After annealing at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour, substrates were brought into a N_2 filled glove box for the perovskite layer deposition.

The perovskite precursor solution was prepared mixing 166 mg FAI, 21.6 mg MABr, 87.1 mg PbBr_2 , 547.4 mg PbI_2 and 19.4 mg of CsI and adding N-N dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at volume ratio of 3.16 and then leaving it to stir for 12 hours at room temperature. The spin coating deposition of the perovskite was performed at 1000 rpm for 10 s followed by a high-speed step at 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. During this last step, 150 μL of CB was dripped as anti-solvent onto the spinning substrate. The samples were annealed at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour.

Spiro-OMeTAD (2,2',7,7'-Tetrakis[N,N-di(4-methoxyphenyl)amino]-9,9'-spirobifluorene) was used as the reference hole transport layer: 16.6 μl of bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt in acetonitrile (Li-TFSI, 520 mg/ml), 7.2 μl of cobalt (III) tris(bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide) (FK-209, 0.25 M in acetonitrile), 27 μL of 4 tert-butylpyridine (TBP) were added to 73.5 mg of spiro-OMeTAD dissolved in 1 ml of chlorobenzene. The solution was spun at 2000 rpm for 20 seconds.

A benzothiadiazole-modified poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl), i.e. BTD-P3HT, in-house synthesised, was also tested as HTM: it was dissolved with a concentration of 12 mg/ml in chlorobenzene and then doped by adding Li-TFSI, TBP, and Co(III)-TFSI, following doping strategy procedure previously reported[30,37]. To prevent any agglomeration, solution was kept stirring at 50 °C for 15 min, then deposited by spin-coating at 6000 rpm for 45 seconds.

The devices were finished by thermally evaporating 90 nm of gold as the top electrode.

Synthesis of BTD-P3HT

The synthesis (a Kumada polycondensation reaction) of the in-house HTM is detailly described in our precedent paper[30] and it is just briefly recalled hereafter: in a Schlenk flask, 4,7-bis(5-bromo-3-hexylthiophen-2-yl)benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole (0.4 g, 0.63 mmol) was mixed with lithium chloride (0.5 M in THF, 1.40 mL, 0.7 mmol) and *i*PrMgCl (2 M in THF, 0.35 mL, 0.7 mmol) in dry THF (1.5 mL) under Argon atmosphere. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. Similarly, 2-bromo-3-hexyl-5-iodothiophene (4.5 g, 12.1 mmol) was mixed with lithium chloride (0.5 M in THF, 26.5 mL, 13.3 mmol), dry THF (65 mL) and *i*PrMgCl (2 M in THF, 6 mL, 12.1 mmol). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. The two solutions obtained were mixed together into a Schlenk flask. Then 0.5% mol of Ni(*i*Pr)(acac)₂, as catalyst, in dry THF solution (10 mmol/L, 6.35 mL) was added and the mixture was thoroughly stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. The polymerization was quenched by adding few drops of aqueous HCl (5 mol/L). The mixture was poured into petroleum ether and stirred for 45 min to precipitate the polymer that was then washed with water and acetone. The product was collected by filtration and then dried in vacuum (800 mbar, 25°C). Yield: 13.55%. ¹H-NMR (128 scan, 50 °C, 600 MHz, CDCl₃, ppm) δ : 6.98 (s, 1H), 2.81 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 1.72 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 1.40 – 1.26 (m, 6H), 0.92 (t, J = 7.3, 5.5, 2.8 Hz, 3H).

Characterisation of films and devices

UV-Vis spectra were measured by using a spectrophotometer (Dymax EC-5000 lamp) in a wavelength range of 300–850 nm.

Current density-voltage (J-V) curves were recorded under illumination by a solar simulator (ABET Sun 2000), set at AM 1.5 and calibrated to $100 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ using a calibrated silicon reference cell. The 4 cells on each $2.5\times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ substrates were measured at the same time, in both forward and reverse direction, with a scan rate of $100 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}$, by a commercial setup of 4-wire source meter and several channels (Arkeo-Ariadne, Cicci Research srl). The active areas were delimited by using black tape masks with apertures of 0.09 cm^2 . Some of the measured J-V curves, especially of the irradiated devices, showed fluctuations, due to contact issues during the scans, possibly due to ageing of the silver paint, added to the thermally evaporated gold contacts to improve the contact resistance. For the sake of clarity and a better readability of the figures, such curves were smoothed via a data analysis and graphing software.

EQE spectra were measured using a commercial setup (Arkeo-Ariadne, Cicci Research srl) based on a 300 W xenon lamp, able to acquire a spectrum from 300 to 1100 nm with a resolution of 2 nm. The same setup, endowed with white LEDs (4100 Kelvin) and a 4-wire source meter, allowed measuring J-V plots at increasing light intensities.

The powder X-ray diffraction patterns (PXRD) were collected with an X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer from PANalytical working in Bragg–Brentano geometry equipped with a $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ source. Scattered photons were revealed by an X'celerator linear detector equipped with a Ni filter to attenuate $\text{K}\beta$.

Neutron irradiation

Films and devices were exposed to fast neutron irradiation at fluence levels of, respectively, $1.39 \times 10^9 \text{ neutrons}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and $1.62 \times 10^{10} \text{ neutrons}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, at room temperature and in the dark.

The samples' side exposed to the incoming neutron flux was the deposited material for the films and the top electrode side for the complete cells. Due to the samples' total thickness (less than $200 \mu\text{m}$, including the plastic substrate) and the penetrating power of neutrons, the side exposed to the incoming flux is not relevant.

Additional Figures

Figure S1. Photovoltaic parameters of flexible cells endowed with BTD-P3HT and spiro-OMeTAD as hole transport materials after fabrication, before being shipped for neutron irradiation. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

Figure S2. **Neutrons energy spectra.** Energy spectrum using the ChipIR beamline compared to energy spectra on the ISS, terrestrial atmosphere and Mars, respectively.

Figure S3. Transmittance of bare PET ITO substrates and SnO₂ films on PET ITO showing no significance variation between control and irradiated samples.

Figure S4. UV-vis absorption as a function of wavelength for control and irradiated films on PET ITO/ SnO₂: (a) perovskite only; (b) perovskite/ spiro-OMeTAD; (c) perovskite/ BTD-P3HT.

Figure S5. (a) XRD spectra of not irradiated perovskite film, perovskite and perovskite/spiro-OMeTAD films after the irradiation at 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻²; asterisks and solid dots indicate the 12.6° PbI_2 and 14.1° perovskite peaks; the spectrum of the PET ITO/ SnO₂ substrate is also reported as it is responsible of the large peak observed at 26° . (b) Ratio between the PbI_2 peak at 12.6° and the perovskite peak at 14.1° for the same films: higher values of this ratio are associated to larger degradation of the perovskite layer.

Figure S6. **Effect of storage time on control cells.** Variation of the average values of PV parameters for the control cells, with either spiro-OMeTAD or BTD-P3HT as the HTL, after storage in a box, in air and in the dark at ambient conditions, for as long as the time needed to ship the other cells to the ISIS, where they were irradiated, and then back. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

Figure S1. **Effect of storage time on control cells.** Cells were tested after fabrication and after being stored in a box, in air and in the dark at ambient conditions, for as long as the time needed to ship the other cells to the ISIS where they were irradiated and then shipped back. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

Figure S8. Effect of neutron irradiation on flexible cells. PV parameters for spiro-OMeTAD (top) and BTD-P3HT (bottom) flexible cells after irradiation at different fluences, i.e. 10^9 and 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻²·s⁻¹, compared to control cells, after storage in dark for 21 days. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

Figure S9. Effect of neutron irradiation on flexible cells. Series and shunt resistances for spiro-OMeTAD (a, c) and BTD-P3HT (b, d) flexible cells after irradiation at different fluences, i.e. 10^9 and 10^{10} neutrons·cm⁻²·s⁻¹, compared to control cells, after storage in dark for 21 days. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

Figure S10. Variation of the average values of PV parameters for the irradiated cells, with either spiro-OMeTAD (a, b) or BTd-P3HT (c, d) as the HTL. (a, c) Irradiated cells are compared to the control cells freshly made. (b, d – already in Figure 3 in the main text) Irradiated cells are compared to the control cells after storage in a box, in air and in the dark at ambient conditions, for as long as the time needed to ship the other cells to the ISIS, where they were irradiated, and then back. Values for both forward (from short to open circuit, blank boxes) and reverse scans (from open to short circuit, patterned boxes) are reported.

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